

Time Resolved Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging System For *In Vivo* Characterization of Tumors

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Abstract: We present a lifetime fluorescence imaging system for small animal imaging. The system uses a linear fiber array with given separations between a single source fiber and several detection fibers. The general goal is to detect and localize tumors, using specific fluorescent markers and investigate their progression. We investigated applications of the developed system to mouse imaging, using as contrast agent Alexa Fluor 750 conjugated to tumor specific antibodies (Herceptin). Realized 2D mapping of fluorescence lifetime indicate lower lifetime value in the tumor area.

Introduction

Fluorescence lifetime is known to be sensitive to an immediate environment of the fluorophore e.g., temperature, pH, oxygen content, nutrient supply and bioenergetic status (1). On the other hand, the fluorescence lifetime is practically independent of the concentration of the fluorescent agent and intensity of the excitation light. The lifetime tends to remain constant even when 5-fold fluctuations in intensity occur (2). The heterogeneity of tumor vasculature can be observed through changes in pH and temperature (3). By selecting fluorophores with known lifetime dependence on pH and / or temperature, this method can potentially be used for functional diagnosis of malignancies and drug targeting.

In this paper, we present a small animal molecular imaging system and its application for *in vivo* mice study. The goal of our study is to develop efficient time-resolved system for *in vivo* imaging using suitable contrast agents in near infrared (NIR) spectral region, which provide spatial distributions of lifetime of fluorescent agent inside the turbid media. We present *in vivo* study on mice to validate the system for future applications to minimally invasive functional imaging.

Materials and Methods:

The schematic diagram of the NIR fluorescence small-animal imaging system is shown in Fig.1, the details of which have been described elsewhere (4).

Briefly, the system was based on a time-domain technique, where an advance time-correlated single-photon counting device was used in conjunction with a high-speed repetition-rate tunable laser to detect individual photons. It used a photomultiplier tube as a detector, and a temperature-controlled scanning stage with an electrocardiogram and temperature monitoring device for small animals, and a scanning head. The scanning head consisted of multimode optical fibers that were used to deliver light from an excitation source and an emitted fluorescence signal to detectors. The imager had a laser source for fluorescence excitation ($\lambda = 750$ nm), an emission filter ($\lambda = 790$ nm) for fluorescence detection, and a computer for data analysis. The imager scanned in a raster pattern over skin or other tissue surfaces to produce a real-time two-dimensional image. A cooled, charge-coupled device (CCD) camera was also used to guide the scan to the region of interest (ROI) and to measure the fluorescence intensity distribution, which helped to locate the tumor inside the tissue. Animal study was performed with athymic female nude mice approximately six to eight weeks old. Breast cancer cells (SK-BR-3) were implanted to flank area of the mice. These cells express high levels of HER2 (HER2/neu, c-ErbB2) protein. In this study, Alexa Fluor 750 (Invitrogen, Inc) was conjugated with Herceptin (Genentach Inc. USA), a HER2-specific monoclonal antibody presently used in clinic for targeted therapy of HER2-overexpressing tumors.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of the imaging system.

To analyze the specific target accumulation of the imaging probe, mice were anesthetized by inhalation of isoflurane. 50 μg of Herceptin conjugates were injected into the tail vein and imaged at predetermined time points after injection.

Fig. 2. Typical fluorescence image at 24 h obtained from mice after injecting herceptin-Alexa Fluor 750 conjugate.

Results:

The reproducibility of the experiments was tested by measuring the lifetime of the fluorophore, Alexa Fluor750 (Invitrogen, Inc, USA), diluted with commonly used solvents, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and pure water. Measurements were performed by placing the solutions sequentially on a mirror to exclude diffuse reflection and photon migration effects. To calculate lifetime, the trailing edges of the curves were best fitted with a single exponential decay. The lifetime measurements were repeated five times in each group under the same conditions at room temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). The lifetime values of Alexa Fluor 750 strongly depend on the solvents and were 1.19 ± 0.007 ns and 0.61 ± 0.006 ns in DMSO and pure water respectively.

Fig. 3. Clearance time of the herceptin conjugated with Alexa fluor 750 in mouse model after the intravenous injection through the vein tail.

Animal Study:

An example of two-dimensional intensity distribution measured by CCD camera at 24 hours after the injection is presented in Fig.2. Fig 3 shows subsequent washout of the fluorophore from the ROI at larger time intervals after the injection. The lifetime of the conjugated fluorophore was calculated over the tumor region by fitting the exponential decay time from the trailing edge of time-resolved intensity distributions at each pixel for all detection fibers. The 3-D lifetime distribution, obtained using mentioned above simplifying assumption of effective depth of photons, reaching individual detection fibers is shown in Fig. 4. In tumor area measured lifetime values are lower than that of surrounding medium, as expected, if pH inside tumor is lower than that of outside.

Fig. 4. Distribution of lifetime values in tumor region at different depth. The lifetime values at the center of the tumor are lower than the surrounding area at 20 hrs after the injection.

Discussion:

Fluorescence lifetime imaging may be applied to non-invasive studies of crucial metabolic-dependent conditions such as O_2 concentration, temperature and pH, from immediate environment in animal models. Combining our lifetime imaging system with known analytical solution for lifetime intensity distributions can make it possible to perform time-resolved lifetime imaging *in vivo* for deeply embedded targets in highly scattering media.

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